

Exploring the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Graphic Design and Digital Marketing Industry in Kolkata

Pritha Bhattacharya

Ph.D. Scholar, Mansarovar Global University

Dr. Bhupinder Pal Singh

Professor, Department of Management, Faculty of Commerce & Management

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 24-05-2025

Published: 10-06-2025

Keywords:

AI tools, Creativity, Job security

ABSTRACT

This study explores the use of AI tools in Kolkata's graphic design and digital marketing sector, based on responses from 50 professionals. Most participants reported frequent AI use, especially tools like ChatGPT and Canva AI, primarily for idea generation and design creation. While AI has improved productivity and eased workflows for many, concerns remain over its creative limitations—64% believe AI designs lack the creativity of human work, and most clients still prefer human-generated content. Importantly, 86% of respondents expressed concern about job security, fearing AI could replace existing roles. The findings underline both the growing reliance on AI and the need to address its impact on creativity and employment

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15663440>

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving digital era, technology is reshaping how individuals, businesses, and industries operate, with marketing and creative communication among the most transformed fields. Digital marketing, using platforms like social media, SEO, and content strategies, has become essential for brand visibility, engagement, and growth—especially as consumer behaviour increasingly shifts online. Amid this shift, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is emerging as a powerful force, enhancing campaign creation, personalization, and optimization to boost impact and efficiency.

AI, through technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision, simulates human intelligence to automate tasks, improve decision-making, and accelerate data analysis. In the creative sector, AI is revolutionizing graphic design and digital marketing by streamlining workflows, generating personalized content, and enhancing productivity. In India's creative hubs like Kolkata, AI adoption is rapidly growing, with agencies, freelancers, and start-ups increasingly leveraging tools like Canva, Adobe Firefly, ChatGPT, and Midjourney to elevate visual storytelling. This study examines AI's evolving role in Kolkata's design and digital marketing scene through literature, professional insights, and field data, highlighting how it is transforming both practices and perceptions.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the extent to which AI tools are being adopted by graphic designers and digital marketers in Kolkata.
2. To explore the perceived advantages and challenges faced by professionals while integrating AI in their creative processes.
3. To analyse the impact of AI on the efficiency, creativity, and output quality of graphic design and digital marketing work.
4. To understand the level of awareness and skill proficiency related to AI tools among creative professionals in Kolkata.
5. To investigate whether AI adoption varies across different types of organizations (freelancers, agencies, start-ups) in the Kolkata design and marketing landscape.

HYPOTHESIS:

1. **H0:** AI tool usage does not significantly improve productivity in graphic design and digital marketing.
H1: AI tool usage significantly improves productivity in graphic design and digital marketing.
2. **H0:** There is no significant relationship between industry experience and the likelihood of adopting AI tools.
H2: There is a significant relationship between industry experience and the likelihood of adopting AI tools.

3. **H0:** There is no significant difference in perceived creativity between AI-generated and human-created designs.

H3: There is a significant difference in perceived creativity between AI-generated and human-created designs.

4. **H0:** Professionals do not believe that AI adoption may lead to the replacement of certain job roles.

H4: Professionals believe that AI adoption may lead to the replacement of certain job roles.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK-

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Fig.1.2 represents conceptual framework

This framework highlights how these variables influence productivity, adoption of AI, client satisfaction, creativity perceptions, and job security concerns. The framework helps guide the study by connecting AI adoption to both practical and professional impacts within the industry.

Assumptions

1. Respondents work in digital marketing or graphic designing industry.
2. Participants have taken part in the study willingly.
3. Respondents have a basic understanding of AI tools relevant to their field.
4. Participants are between the ages 21- 60 years.
5. Perceptions and impacts shared are influenced by current trends and tools, not hypothetical or outdated systems.

LIMITATIONS

1. The study is geographically limited to professionals based in **Kolkata**, and findings may not reflect trends in other regions.
2. Responses are self-reported and may carry **bias or subjectivity**.
3. Time and resource constraints may limit the sample size or diversity of respondents.
4. The sample size is limited to between ages 21-60

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Participants are **aged between 21 and 60 years**.
2. Participants are professionals, currently working or freelancing in **graphic design** or **digital marketing**.
3. Participants are based in **Kolkata** or working with clients in the Kolkata region.
4. Participants are willing to participate voluntarily and provide informed responses for academic research purposes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Bastray et al. (2025) examined the integration of AI in digital marketing, noting its role in personalization, engagement, and performance tracking, while also addressing ethical concerns and the need for skilled talent.

Marvi et al. (2025) explored AI's evolution in marketing, categorizing it into mechanical, thinking, and feeling AI, highlighting its role in personalization and decision-making, and calling for further research on socio-economic impacts.

Lesse et al. (2024) discussed AI's contribution to digital marketing and sustainability, showing how it enhances content creation, lead generation, customer experience, and environmental outcomes. **Alshurideh et al. (2023)** reviewed digital marketing tools and strategies like e-WOM, SEO, and social media, emphasizing their effect on customer experience in the digital era. Sharabati and Hussein (2023) provided a bibliometric analysis of AI in digital marketing, identifying trends and challenges, and emphasizing AI's role in personalization and outreach optimization. **Bashang & Puttanna (2023)** explained how AI helps businesses analyse data and personalize engagement, transforming marketing strategies.

Meng (2012) highlighted AI's role in graphic design, from automating tasks to generating concepts, while also raising concerns over human displacement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the approach taken to study how artificial intelligence (AI) is influencing the graphic design and digital marketing industry in Kolkata. The research aims to explore the extent of AI adoption, its perceived benefits and challenges, and its overall impact on creativity, workflow, and client engagement. A mixed-methods approach was used, combining quantitative surveys from industry professionals and digital marketers with qualitative interviews to gain deeper insights. The study also incorporates secondary data from recent reports and journals to support findings and provide broader context.

- 1. Research approach:** Qualitative & quantitative mixed method.
- 2. Research design:** Descriptive Survey
- 3. Sampling technique:** Non- probability sampling.

In this case, purposive sampling technique was used to select participants who are actively engaged in graphic designing and digital marketing roles in Kolkata and have experience or familiarity with AI tools. This approach ensured that the data collected was relevant to the objectives of the study. In cases where direct access was limited, snowball sampling was also employed to reach additional qualified respondents through professional referrals.

- 4. Setting:** The study was conducted in Kolkata.
- 5. Sample Size:** 50

DATA COLLECTION:

Surveys : Structured questionnaire was developed for both online and offline data collection. The survey aimed to capture insights from professionals in the graphic design and digital marketing industry in Kolkata, focusing on their experiences with and perspectives on the use of AI tools in their work.

VARIABLES AND MEASUREMENTS OF THE STUDY:

Independent Variables: Frequency of AI usage, purpose of AI usage, level of AI integration in workflow, and level of AI-related knowledge or training.

Dependent Variables: AI impact on creativity, productivity, client satisfaction, job role transformation, and perception of AI as a threat or opportunity.

Demographic variables: Age, gender, professional role, years of experience, educational background, and type of organization.

Tools for data collection: The tools for data collection will be under three parts-

1. **Part I:** It consists of socio demographic variables. Socio demographic variables of this study are- Age, gender, professional role, years of experience, educational background, and type of organization.
2. **Part II:** A structured questionnaire was developed to assess AI impact on creativity, productivity, client satisfaction, job role transformation, and perception of AI as a threat or opportunity.
3. **Part III:** A 5- point Likert scale was developed to assess the perception of the professionals on the impact of AI

RESULTS:

This section presents the findings derived from the survey responses collected from professionals in the graphic designing and digital marketing industry of Kolkata. The data has been analysed to address the research objectives and test the hypotheses related to AI adoption, its impact on productivity, creativity, and industry practices.

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES:

SL no.	Demographic variable	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age group in years		
	21-30	16	32%
	31-40	18	36%
	41-50	11	22%
	51-60	5	10%
2	Gender		
	Male	28	56%
	Female	22	44%
3	Education Status		
	Undergraduate	11	22%
	Graduate	33	66%
	Post Graduate	6	12%
4	Professional Role		
	Graphic Designer	19	38%
	Digital Marketer	16	32%
	Creative Director	4	8%
	Editor	11	22%
5	Organization Type		
	Freelancer	9	18%
	Design/ Marketing agency	20	40%
	Corporate/ In house team	21	42%
6	Industry Experience		
	< 1 year	9	18%
	1-4 years	23	46%
	>4 years	18	36%

Table 2.1 represents the demographic data and analysis

DATA ANALYSIS:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly reshaping creative industries across the globe, including graphic design and digital marketing. India's AI market is expected to hit \$17 billion by 2027, growing at 25–

35% annually, while the global AI marketing market could exceed \$107 billion by 2028. Meanwhile, the World Economic Forum predicts that AI will transform nearly 23% of jobs worldwide by 2027.

Now from the given structured questionnaire on AI adoption and impact, the following data was obtained-

The data indicates that the majority of respondents, at **50%**, consider themselves to have **intermediate** proficiency in using AI tools. This is followed by **beginners**, who make up **26%** of the sample. **Advanced** users account for **18%**, while only **6%** identify as **experts**. This suggests that while AI adoption is growing, most professionals are still in the learning or mid-level stage of proficiency.

Fig. 1.3 represents the AI proficiency of the respondents

The data also reveals widespread adoption of AI among professionals, with 96% reporting usage—most using it occasionally, and 30% relying on it heavily. A significant majority (72%) feel that AI has made their work easier, though some remain uncertain. However, when it comes to creative quality, 64% believe AI-generated designs fall short compared to human-made ones. This skepticism is echoed on the client side, with 84% of respondents stating that clients prefer human-created content, reinforcing a continued preference for human creativity in the industry. The data shows 86% of respondents believe AI is negatively impacting jobs by replacing roles, indicating strong concern about job displacement in Kolkata’s creative industry.

ChatGPT (92%) and Canva AI (68%) emerged as the most widely used tools, reflecting their accessibility and relevance in design and marketing. Others like Adobe Firefly (34%), Midjourney (24%), Jasper AI (16%), and tools such as Hubspot, Copy.ai, Dall·E, and Gemini

(mentioned in 'Other' category) were used to a lesser extent, catering to more specific needs.

Fig. 1.4 represents the AI tools used by the respondents

60% of the respondents use AI tools for idea generation, making it the most common application, followed by 56% for design generation, and 32% for image editing. Copywriting accounts for 24%, while video creation/ editing is at 20%, and marketing campaign creation is the

least common at 16%.

Fig. 1.5 represents the types of work in which AI is used by the respondents

Among 50 respondents, 52% cited lack of control, 40% noted quality drop, and 38% faced inaccurate results. Other issues included limited personalization (30%), ethical concerns (18%), and adoption difficulty (14%). Only 4% reported no challenges.

Fig. 1.6 represents the challenges in AI adoption by the respondents

LIKERT SCALE DATA:

From the Likert scale, it was seen that most respondents view AI positively: 72% said it improved productivity, 84% found it useful for idea generation and workflow, 54% felt it enhanced creative quality, and 68% saw better client satisfaction. However, only 34% believed AI users are setting new industry standards, indicating its impact is valued but not yet seen as transformative.

HYPOTHESES TESTING:

1. **H0: AI tool usage does not significantly improve productivity in graphic design and digital marketing.**

72% of respondents agreed that AI tools improve productivity, while only 6% disagreed and 22% were neutral. This strong positive perception leads to the rejection of H0 and acceptance of **H1: AI tool usage significantly improves productivity.**

2. **H0: There is no significant relationship between industry experience and likelihood of adopting AI tools.**

A chi-square test between age group and AI usage frequency yielded a p-value of 0.0013 (< 0.05), indicating a significant relationship. Hence, H₀ is rejected and **H2: There is a significant relationship between industry experience and AI adoption** is accepted.

3. **H0: There is no significant difference in perceived creativity between AI and human-created designs.**

64% believe AI designs are less creative; only 6% view them as more creative. This clear preference for human creativity leads to rejection of H₀ and acceptance of **H3: A significant difference exists in perceived creativity between AI and human designs.**

4. **H0: Professionals do not believe AI adoption may replace certain job roles.**
86% believe AI is displacing jobs, while only 8% see it creating new ones. This strong concern about job loss leads to rejection of H₀ and acceptance of **H4: Professionals believe AI adoption may lead to job role replacement.**

CONCLUSION:

This study explores the impact of AI on the graphic design and digital marketing industry in Kolkata by surveying 50 professionals across various organizational roles and experience levels. The findings indicate that AI adoption is widespread, with 96% of respondents using AI tools in their workflow. Tools like ChatGPT and Canva AI emerged as the most popular, primarily used for idea generation and visual design tasks. While most professionals acknowledge improvements in productivity and ease of work, the majority still believe that AI-generated designs lack the creativity of human-made content. Concerns over job displacement remain prominent, with 86% expressing fears of AI replacing roles. Despite its growing role in the industry, AI is still seen as an aid rather than a replacement for human

creativity and judgment. Hypothesis testing further supports that AI enhances productivity, is influenced by user experience levels, and impacts perceptions of creativity and job security.

LIMITATIONS

1. **Sample Size:** The study was conducted with a relatively small sample (n=50), which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader industry.
2. **Geographic Scope:** Since the research is confined to Kolkata, the results may not reflect trends in other cities or regions of India.
3. **Self-Reported Data:** The study relies on self-reported perceptions, which can introduce biases in responses, particularly around sensitive topics like job displacement.
4. **Tool Diversity:** While key tools were covered, newer or lesser-known AI tools may not have been adequately captured in the responses.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Skill Development:** With most users identifying as intermediate or beginner, there's a need for targeted upskilling programs focused on AI tools tailored for creative professionals.
2. **Client Education:** Since a majority of clients still prefer human-generated content, efforts should be made to educate them on AI capabilities and potential through pilot projects or blended creative approaches.
3. **Human-AI Collaboration:** Organizations should promote workflows that combine human creativity with AI efficiency to preserve originality while improving output.
4. **Ethical Guidelines:** Given the concerns around control and accuracy, there should be industry-level guidelines for responsible and ethical AI usage in creative tasks.
5. **Job Transition Support:** As AI integration reshapes roles, reskilling programs and transparent communication can help manage transitions and reduce fears of job loss.

REFERENCES

- Alshurideh, M., Urabi, S., & Al Kurdi, B. (2023). Digital Marketing Strategies and the Impact on Customer Experience: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(2), e01372.
- Bashang, S., & Puttanna, K. (2023). The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Marketing: A Review. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Management Studies*, 2(3), 125–133.
- Bastray, T., Babu, S. R., Mahesh, G., & Kanumuri, V. V. (2025). The Integration of AI in Digital Marketing: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 5(1).
- Marvi, R., Foroudi, P., & Cuomo, M. T. (2025). Past, present and future of AI in marketing and knowledge management. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 29(11), 1-31.
- Meng, X. (2012). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Graphic Design Industry. *Res Militaris*.
- Leese, M., & Russell, A. (2024). Artificial Intelligence in Digital Marketing Within the Framework of Sustainable Management. *Sustainability*, 16(23), 10511.
- Sharabati, A. A., & Hussein, A. A. (2023). Artificial Intelligence in Digital Marketing: Insights from a Comprehensive Review. *Electronics*, 12(12), 2664.